

Influence of Social Media Use on the Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

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Abstract

The tenacity of this research study is to examine the influence of Social Media use on the Academic Performance of undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of education, Port Harcourt. Five Research questions and one Research hypotheses guided the study. To achieve this, the descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study focused on Ignatius Ajuru University of education, Port Harcourt hence, population consists of all the 12,000 full-time undergraduate students 2017/2018 session. The simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 378 students. A four point Likert Type Rating Scale Questionnaire type titled: Social Media and Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students (SMAAPOUS) was used to collect data from the participants. The descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage were used to analyze the demographic data while inferential statistics of Chi-square(x²) was used in testing the research hypotheses. Research findings showed that a great number of students of Ignatius Ajuru University of education are addicted to social media. To this end, the researcher recommended that social media should be used for educational purposes as well, Social Networking Sites should be expanded and new pages should be created to enhance academic activities and avoid setbacks in the students' academic performance, and Students should be monitored by teachers and parents on how they use these sites. This is to create a balance between social media and academic activities of students to avoid setbacks in the academic performance of the students.

Keywords: Social media, Academic performance, Students, Social Networking Sites.

INTRODUCTION

Presently, the world is acclaiming the expansion in communication technology which has enlarged the possibility of communication through Information and Communication Technology (ICT). ICTs consist of internet, satellite television, cable data transmission and computer assisted equipments as observed by Ufuophu and Ayobami (2012).

Social network as a connotation is made up of individuals or organisations called "nodes" which are linked by one or more explicit kinds of interdependency, such as companionship, kinship, mutual interest, monetary exchange, displeasure, voluptuous relationships or affairs of beliefs, awareness or reputation. Social network can also be referred to as a map of specified ties, such as companionship, amid the nodes being studied. The knots in which a specific individual is connected to, are the shared acquaintances of the person, the network measures the collective funds an individual gets from the social network. Social networking sites include: Yahoo Messenger, Facebook Messenger, Blackberry Messenger (BBM), Google talk, Google+ Messenger, iPhone, Androids Twitter, and so on. These networking sites are used by most people to interact with old and new friends, physical or internet friends (Adeboye cited in Asemah and Edegoh, 2012).

The increase in technology has as well affected internet software leading to chatting sites known as social media. With these networking sites, messages can be sent and received virtually instantly but however, absence of directives on how the internet should be used has led to its disproportionate use.

The advancement of internet technology has led to its use as the superlative medium for communication whereby two-third of the world's internet population visits social networking or blogging sites, thus aiding as a communication and linking tool. Social networking sites are working group of internet consumers that interacts with other consumers about areas of joint interest, which could be from a personal, business or academic viewpoint (William, Boyd, Densten, Chin, Diamond and Morgenthaler 2009). Loads of social networking sites have changed the view of worldwide community into an authenticity whereby millions of individuals interconnect through social networking sites. Copious profits have been attained through aloof communication over the usage of social networking sites.

Most undergraduate students possess Facebook accounts and additional social networking handles and as a result countless digits of students perform poorly in school. Bello 2012. Although several intellectuals might be too forward to blame the poor quality of teachers, they might have to think even harder if they have not heard of the Facebook rage (Oche and Aminu, 2010). These days' students are so immersed in the social media that they are practically 24 hours online. Even in classrooms and lecture halls, it has been observed that some students are always busy pinging or facebooking while lectures are ongoing. Periods that should have been dedicated to learning, educational exploration and updating of knowledge have been subdued by the craving for meeting new friend's online, and most times busy deliberating on insignificant issues. Hence most students' academics suffer setback as a result of distraction from the social media. In (Obi, Bulus, Adamu and Sala'at, 2012), it was observed that the use of these sites also affects students' use of English and grammar. The students are used to short forms of writing words in their chat rooms; they forget and use the same in the classrooms and examination. They use things like 4 in place of for, u in place of you, d in place of the etc. and this could affect their class assessment.

Social networking sites have been acknowledged as an important resource for education. Studies shows that students use social networking sites such as Instagram and other sites for entertainment, relaxation, to make new friends etc. (Ellison, Steinfield, and Lampe 2007). Though it has been noted that students devotes much time in participating on social networking activities with many students blaming the numerous social networking sites for their steady decrease in evaluation point averages (Kimberly, Jeong and Lee, 2009), it also expresses that only few students are conscious of the academic and proficient networking openings these sites offers.

Social network websites grab the mind of students and then divert it into non-educational and inappropriate actions including useless chatting. Kuppuswamy and Shankar (2010). Tinto (1997) maintained that extracurricular activities and academic activities are not sufficient to satisfy some students who suffer from social networking isolation. This indicates that social networks are useful for the students as it contributes in their learning capabilities as well as in their academic life. The Internet is no doubt an advancement of technology but precisely social networks are tremendously unsafe for teenagers, social networks became hugely common and well-known in the past few years. Trusov, Bucklin and Pauwels (2009). According to Cain (2009), social network websites provide effortlessness of connecting people to one another, cost free and after connecting one can post news, informative materials, videos and pictures etc. Wiley and Sisson (2006) argued that the prior studies have found that more than 90% of tertiary school students use social networks. In the same way Ellison et al (2007) stated that students use social networking websites approximately 30 minutes throughout the day as a part of their daily life routine. This affirmation shows the importance of social networking websites in the life of a student.

Social networking has changed the way people interact with each other forever. Social networking first existed as an invention created in 1975 known as email, which is still used today (Email). However social networking has advanced into using a profile to give information about a user and his or her interests, and has integrated the use of email. Now social networking involves sharing stories, photos, and involves the use of apps as well as messaging to communicate with others. This type of social networking did not become popular until the year 2003 when Myspace and Friendster were launched. Shortly after Facebook was launched but was not open to the general public until 2006, which has become the number one social networking site today. These networks have many positive effects such as remaining in contact with friends, meeting new people, providing educational benefits, as well as the convenience of mobilly accessing it. Also there are some negative effects which include identity theft, cyber bullying, decreased social interaction in real life, and social isolation. Increase in mobile social networking could possible cause future health problems.

Objectives of the Study

The aim and objective of this study generally is to examine the influence of Social Media on the academic performance of students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. Precisely, the study seeks to;

1. Find out the difference in student's usage of social media network by gender.
2. Verify if age has influence on student's usage of social media network.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. Is there gender difference in the student's usage of social media network?
2. In what ways do younger and older students has been influenced on the use of social media?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis is formulated to guide the conduct of the study.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean response ratings on the student's exposure to social media network and their academic performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is descriptive survey. This design was considered appropriate because it enables the researcher generate data through the standardized collection procedures based on highly structured research instrument(s) and well defined study concepts and related variables.

Population of the Study

The population of this research comprises all the full time undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in 2017/2018 session. The undergraduate students were chosen because they are considered capable of using social media more often. Based on the data obtained from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education registry, the 2017/2018 undergraduate student's total population is 12,000 undergraduate full time students.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A total sample size of this study of 378 were randomly selected using confidence interval of 5 and confidence level of 95% (0.05) from the total population of 12,000 full-time students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. ($378 \div 12,000 = 0.0315 \times 12,000 = 378$)

Research Instrument

A well-constructed self-developed questionnaire titled Social Media and Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students (SMAAPOUS) was administered in two sections; A – Personal data collection and B – the response pattern will be structured in line with the modified four point Likert scale of:

Strongly agree (4 points)
Agree (3 points)
Disagree (2 points)
Strongly disagree (1 point)

There is twenty (20) items in the questionnaire and it was administered in two sections. Section A and Section B. Section A was on demographic data while Section B was on the answer the research questions. Questions 1-4 answers the question to research question number 1, questions 5-8 answers the question to research question number 2, questions 9-12 answers the question to research question number 3, questions 13-16 answers the question to research question number 4 and questions 17-20 answers the question to research question number 5.

Validity of the Instrument

The designed questionnaire was submitted to the project supervisor for vetting, correction and approval before distributing it to the respondents.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the research instrument was determined using a split half test using the odd and even numbered items to form the two halves. The two halves were administered to a sample of students from a university not selected for the main study. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. A co-efficient value of 0.65 indicated that the research instrument was reliable.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher collected the needed data through the use of questionnaire and its administration in the selected faculties. The administration of the questionnaire was carried out by the researcher. A total of 378 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to elicit responses from the students and retrieved on the spot by the researcher. A total of 32 questionnaires were missing while 22 were wrongly filled leaving the researcher with 324 valid questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, and inferential statistics of Chi-square(χ^2). Items with the mean score of $4+3+2+1=10/4=2.5$ and above were considered as adequate; those with mean score below 2.5 were considered as inadequate while the inferential statistics of Chi-square(χ^2) was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: Is there gender difference in the student's usage of social media network?

Table 1: Gender Usage of Social Media

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	Male and female students use social media networks differently in different frequencies.	80 (24%)	201 (62%)	14 (4%)	29 (10%)	324 (100%)
2	Female students use social networking sites more to explicitly foster social connections.	217 (67%)	85 (27%)	0 (0)	22 (6%)	324 (100%)
3	Gender determines the level of social media network usage.	35 (11%)	231 (71%)	19 (6%)	39 (12%)	324 (100%)
4	Males are more effective at using social networking sites for nonacademic purposes.	197 (61%)	56 (17%)	51 (16%)	20 (6%)	324 (100%)
Total		529	573	84	110	1296
Percentage %		(41%)	(44%)	(7%)	(8%)	(100%)

Table 1 shows that 529 of the participants' response strongly Agree that there is a significant difference between male and female student usage of social media network, 573 Agree, 84 Disagree, while 110 Strongly Disagree.

Research Question 2: In what ways do younger and older students has been influenced on the use of social media?

Table 2: Age Usage of Social Media

S/N	Items	SA	A	SD	D	Total
5	Age has impact on the use of social media.	138 (43%)	111 (34%)	17 (5%)	58 (18%)	324 (100%)
6	Social media become boring as I grow older.	18 (6%)	270 (83%)	23 (7%)	13 (4%)	324 (100%)
7	Social media is not relevant to people of older generation.	35 (11%)	34 (10%)	102 (32%)	153 (47%)	324 (100%)
8	The younger generations are the most active users of social media.	215 (66%)	78 (24%)	31 (10%)	0 (0)	324 (100%)
Total		406	493	173	224	1296
Percentage %		(31%)	(38%)	(13%)	(18%)	(100%)

Table 2 indicates that 406 of the participants' response strongly Agree that there is a significant difference between student's usage of social media network by age and their academic performance, 493 Agree, 173 Disagree, while 224 Strongly Disagree.

CONCLUSION

The outcome from the findings of this study shows that, though Social media has negative effects on teenagers such as lack of privacy, distracting students from their academic work, taking most of their productive time and so on, they also have benefits and can be used aptly such as, students can structure online communities in order to plan for a project, have group discussions about class materials, or use the Social networking sites(SNS) as a way to keep in contact with fellow student who has been absent and needs to be updated on current academic information.

The findings of this study and previous ones showed some remarkable results. The first independent variable influencing the academic performance of students which is, social media participation was negatively related with student's outcome while the other independent variables were positively related with student's outcome. The result of this study suggests that lecturers should come up with a pattern on how their students can exploit the benefits of Social media, that school administration should incorporate rules and regulations on the use of the social media in the schools

and that the government should put in place sufficient organized measures to standardize social media use among students and lecturers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

1. Students should be educated on the influence of Social media on their academic performance.
2. Students should be able to manage their study time and avert distractions that come with the use of social media. The number of time used in surfing the net should be reduced.
3. Teachers should endeavor to use social media as a channel to advance the academic performance of students in schools.
4. Social Networking Sites should be stretched out and new pages should be created to increase academic activities and eschew impediments in the student's academic performance.
5. Students should create a sense of balance between chit-chatting and academic activities. More concentration should be directed to research.
6. The use of Social media network by students should be centered on the academic significance of those sites instead of using them for negative motives.
7. Students mainly those ready to record mammoth academic achievement should guard themselves against the successive utilization of social media.

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